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Internationalization of Andalusian companies during the last decade: reasons and perspectives

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to contribute to research on internationalization of companies from the perspective of strategic analysis applied to the factors that influence internationalization decisions.

The literature on internationalization of companies is extensive but mainly focused on theories of internationalization, modes of entry into new markets, and the design of international strategies. It is surprising that the factors that motivate and initiate this whole process have not been studied with such depth, nor applied empirically to the reality of internationalized companies.

This study makes an exhaustive review of the existing literature on the reasons for internationalization and presents a classification of the main groups of reasons that influence these decisions. Although several useful classifications had already been exposed by some authors, one of the main contributions of this research is to place internationalization within the framework of the strategic analysis study. In this way, it is not only possible to categorize the reasons for internationalization, but also to determine the nature and origin of each of them. Thus, it is possible to detect what conditioning factors and players should be considered when designing an internationalization strategy, with the aim of making it more precise and adapted to the real competitive environment of each company.

The value and originality of this study is that by applying a theoretical framework based on existing classifications on internationalization reasons, an empirical study is carried out using a group of companies that have developed internationalization processes in a specific geographical and time frame.

This research shows that, in the case of the companies studied, the competitive environment as a whole has influenced the motivational factors that drive

internationalization decisions, confirming that companies are part of a very broad and complex competitive environment in which all environments -company, microenvironment and macroenvironment- and factors -internal, mixed and external- should be equally considered.

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this work is to contribute to the knowledge of the study of the processes of internationalization of firms. More specifically, contribute to a better knowledge of the reasons that drive organizations to develop internationalization activities.

The study of reasons why companies decide to enter international markets is important for several aspects. Firstly, it serves as internal knowledge of the organization of its decision-making systems, strategic marketing and business management. Secondly, it helps to develop internationalization strategies more adapted to the real situation of companies and their competitive environment. And finally, it helps to design useful policies to promote and support the internationalization of companies and economies.

The literature on international business focuses on internationalization theories and models, methods of entry into foreign markets, the different types of international companies, and the dilemma between standardization and adaptation of the international strategy. But only a few authors have researched the origins of this process, the reasons that make companies decide to work in foreign markets. With internationalization companies jump out from their comfort zone in the local market and face new cultural, economic, commercial, competitive, legislative, and even political challenges. So, internationalization is not a piece of cake and reasons deserve to be studied.

This paper intends to provide more information on the reasons for internationalization using as a framework of study the Andalusian companies that have carried out internationalization activities in recent years. The autonomous region of Andalusia, within the economic framework of Spain and the European Union, has been

in recent years a great example of internationalization of its companies and economy (Revista APD, 2018).

Considering only the exports of goods from 2009 to 2017, the exports of Andalusian companies went from 14,477 to 30,913 million euros, from 9.89% to 19.92% of the Andalusian GDP (Datosmarco Expansión, 2019). Of the 17 autonomous regions that make up Spain, in 2008 Andalusia ranked fifth in the national export ranking, and in 2017 it occupied the second position (ICEX, 2019). The total number of Andalusian export companies went from 16,591 to 24,107 companies from 2009 to 2018 (Extenda, 2019).

Therefore, we can consider that using Andalusian companies in this study can give us a useful insight into the reasons that have driven them to internationalize in recent years. In addition, we can find answers to why in recent years the process of internationalization has been much more decisive and powerful than in previous periods (Pérez-Suárez and Bustelo, 2014). It should be noted that internationalization has affected all types of companies in Andalusia, small and medium enterprises (SMEs), large corporations, social economy companies and cooperatives, products and services companies, and business-to-consumer and business-to-business companies.

We must highlight the role of SMEs -companies with less than 250 employees- in the Andalusian economy and its internationalization. Almost 99% of companies in Andalusia are SMEs and around 90% are micro-companies -companies with less than 10 employees- (Ministerio de Economía, Industria y Competitividad, 2018; INE, 2019).

This paper aims to be useful with two objectives. The first objective is to contribute to the general literature on reasons for business internationalization, analyzing a group of companies that in recent years have developed international activities, and therefore the arguments for internationalization must still be clear in the minds of managers and professionals. The second objective is to fill the gap in the specific literature on the

internationalization of Spanish and Andalusian companies in terms of which drivers have taken them to new markets.

This paper is composed of an exhaustive study of the existing literature on international business and internationalization, focusing mainly on the factors and components that influence the reasons for carrying out this process. The concept of internationalization is contextualized and delimited, the term is framed in the field of business studies, and the importance of the reasons for internationalization for a coherent business strategy is explained. Through the review of the literature, the proposals of other authors are summarized and classified to find a useful theoretical framework applicable to the reality of the companies that are the object of this study.

For this study, primary information has been collected through a questionnaire sent to executives of Andalusian companies that have developed international activities in the last ten years. After the analysis of the information a discussion of the results, conclusions and managerial recommendations for practical application of the results are presented.

2. Literature review

2.1 Internationalization in recent years

The advances experienced in the last decades in terms of information technologies, transportation of people and goods, deregulation of many international markets and the processes of economic integration developed by many countries and economic blocs, have driven the will of many companies to grow beyond their borders through international trade activities (Oviatt and McDougall, 2005; Keegan and Green, 2017). These changes of technological nature and in the global economy have led to the development of internationalization business strategies by those companies whose main objective was business growth. These organizations have found in economic, technological and social globalization, a wide variety of options to pursue their growth objective by developing their business internationally (Becerra, 2010).

Currently, the phenomenon of internationalization not only affects companies that have already consolidated their position in their local markets, or large companies that have the financial resources to enter new markets. Globalization and new technologies have allowed small organizations to develop international activities and work with foreign clients and suppliers (Navío, 2007).

Commercial growth through internationalization activities is directly related to the interrelation of factors that are external to the organization and the capacities and resources that it has acquired or developed over time. But also, organizations must be aware of the characteristics and needs of the target markets, as well as understand the external and internal factors that affect the company before deciding to enter new international markets (Canals, 1994).

Considering the global changes mentioned as factors that are framed in a general and external context, together with the existence of factors that are specific to each organization or that depend directly on the decisions of the Management of companies, we can see a first approach to the external and internal influences in making business decisions related to international markets. Using the versatile analysis offered by the SWOT matrix, we can say that, like other business analyses, internationalization decisions are influenced by external factors, opportunities and threats, and by internal factors, strengths and weaknesses.

In recent decades, despite deregulation, agreements on international trade and the open effects of globalization, the global economic landscape has been characterized by uncertainty and turbulence in the form of economic crises and trade conflicts. These conditions have led companies to seek new growth alternatives, to consolidate in foreign markets and to diversify risks (Bradley and Calderón, 2006). Therefore, it would be feasible to propose that in times of crisis, and despite its negative effects on the economic structure of many countries and companies, business dynamics and decisions are reoriented to seek solutions that allow companies to continue growing either within their local markets or beyond their national borders.

We can also propose that just as living beings struggle for survival and growth in times of difficulty, companies, which are ultimately made up of human beings, also seek alternatives for survival and growth in difficult times. When the business environment becomes hostile or presents barriers to the growth objectives desired by companies, the people who make up the company transfer their human character and sense of survival and improvement to the managerial decisions that guide the strategic orientation of the organization.

The reasons for internationalization can be very varied and it is important to analyse different aspects of the process of internationalization of companies (Benito, 2015). The reasons for internationalization can have a double dimension. An objective dimension based on exploitation and exploration of resources, and a subjective dimension based on the psychological approach of the search for better market conditions (Cuervo-Cazurra, Narula and Un, 2015). Just like the human condition, in internationalization decisions, objective and subjective decision elements both play an important role. Perhaps, for this reason, it is difficult to establish a generally accepted classification of motives, and it is also difficult to get clear answers from executives about the origins of their international strategy.

In the last decade, companies with growth objectives, both locally and internationally, have had additional difficulties to achieve their goals. According to the World Trade Organization, the 2008 financial crisis caused a decline in international trade flows of 12% and a fall of 5.4% of world GDP at the end of 2008. In the following years the situation worsened in many countries and regions. The fall in credit offered by financial institutions to companies and the economic uncertainty suffered by consumers caused the decrease of international trade (Chor and Manova, 2012).

It has been generally assumed that international trade offers benefits to countries (Prowse, 2002). Possibly as a response to the dark economic panorama and the drastic credit cut, many governments and public agencies launched programs to support the internationalization of companies. These programs could be interpreted as part of the country's competitiveness policies (Porter, 2011; Keegan and Green, 2017). These programs offer services that partially replace financial market deficiencies, with diagnostic, information, education, consulting, and financial support programs (ICEX,

2019; Extenda, 2019; Jetro, 2019; Kotra, 2019; Agenzia ICE, 2019; Cansino, Lopez-Melendo, Pablo-Romero and Sánchez-Braza, 2013).

2.2 Internationalization concept, expansion and entry strategies, and reasons

Regardless of whether a company uses new or existing products or services, using the Ansoff matrix (1957) we can frame the internationalization activities of companies in strategies focused on new markets. More specifically in the strategies focused on developing new international markets beyond national borders where the company carries out its activity traditionally. That is, the opening of geographic markets in addition to the national market in which the company is already present and where it was founded.

According to market expansion strategies that use the dimensions of concentration and diversification of markets and countries, in the case of internationalization we would refer to the strategies of country diversification and global diversification (Ayal and Zif, 1979). In the first, the company focuses on a type of market segment diversifying the countries. In the second, the firm develops a strategy in which serves several segments in multiple countries, that is, diversification in both customers and countries (Keegan and Green, 2017).

To establish a clear scenario we can define the internationalization of companies as the process through which an organization, considering its resources and capabilities and the opportunities and threats, participates in the reality of globalization to project its activities, partially or totally, in an international environment for the generation of transactions between different countries (Leandro, 2009). Although flows are mainly commercial, economic and financial, internationalization activities also generate

knowledge flows such as the dissemination of commercial, technological and management know-how.

For Arteaga Ortiz (2017) internationalization guides the commercial and productive activity of organizations towards activities that take place outside the markets that are traditionally their natural geographical environment.

Other authors such as Larrinaga (2005) provide additional concepts and expand the factors that intervene in the concept. The entry strategy can be defined as a business development strategy by geographical diversification, through a long-term evolutionary process that affects company's structure and activities of the value chain.

Focusing on export and entrepreneurial behaviour of managers, Ibeh and Young (2001) and Navarro-García, Schmidt and Rey-Moreno (2015) use the concept of *export entrepreneurship* as the process by which people and companies take advantage of market opportunities considering the available resources and the environmental constraints. Following this definition, the authors differentiate between external and internal factors on which the company would depend to make its internationalization decisions.

Despite not having a generally accepted definition, for Azuayi (2016) internationalization is the process by which companies develop activities in international markets, a process marked by a situation of "severe competition for the companies". This process would be motivated by the fact that the local market is less attractive compared to new international markets, and because managers decide to operate in new markets to continue the expansion with the following ones.

Considering these definitions, we see that common concepts appear and can be classified into two basic and general dimensions that make up the concept of internationalization. Concepts such as people, managers' decisions, resources and capabilities, company's structure, and activities of the value chain would belong to the

internal sphere of the organization. Other factors such as new markets, international environment, opportunities and threats, and environmental constraints would be part of the sphere external to the company. And we could add a third classification formed by concepts that have dual components. It would be a combination of reasons such as competition and market attractiveness that depend on external factors, but also on the capabilities and resources of the firm itself.

Internationalization decisions made by a company involve medium and long-term activities with the objective of establishing productive and/or commercial activities in another country. The internationalization strategy can consist of several options that allow companies to operate outside their country of origin or domestic market (Johnson, Scholes, Whittington and Frery, 2011).

Due to this double commercial and productive orientations, we must also highlight the types of actions that make up the internationalization activities. The wide variety of international activities that companies can develop can be classified into two main areas: export activities and investment activities. With the development of the literature on internationalization, the concepts of exporting and foreign direct investment (FDI) have been the most widespread (Hollensen, 2017).

The FDI can take several forms, such as direct investments in the development of own productive or commercial structures in other countries, or financial investments in total or partial acquisitions of existing structures. The internationalization processes have promoted different legal forms of collaboration and shared ownership. These collaboration models have been used by all types of companies including SMEs to overcome barriers and achieve growth (Lu and Beamish, 2006; Hessels and Parker, 2013).

Another form of foreign investment is foreign indirect investment. This type of investment has been extended in recent years as another option for internationalization of

companies (Barbé Izuel, 2010). It consists of the granting of loans or a set of loans from international organizations or multilateral institutions to governments of countries in which the investment project will be carried out. This project will be developed by companies not resident in the destination country. The government receives the loan benefits because the investment project is carried out in its territory and international companies receive payment for the products or services provided for the project. This multilateral system promotes international trade flows, but also the economic and social progress of recipient countries (World Bank, 2017). Multilateral institutions offer financial support for export and investment activities, although co-financing of projects by companies with private resources is usually also required. Some of the main multilateral institutions are the World Bank, regional development banks, United Nations and its agencies, and the European Investment Bank (Arteaga Ortiz, 2017).

Another investment option in foreign markets that is rarely mentioned in the literature is the indirect FDI. It consists of doing productive or financial investments through intermediaries or partner companies. It can be done through subsidiaries permanently established in the destination market, or through provisional entities created *ex professo* (Kalotay, 2012).

Regarding the reasons for conducting FDI or indirect FDI as internationalization methods, according to Alzinger and Bellak (1999), FDI is more determined by labour costs, while indirect FDI is more related to a market seeking investment. Both reasons could be included in the internal traditional set of reasons proposed by Dunning (1993).

Extensive literature has been developed to explain and classify the different options and modes of internationalization strategies. Several alternatives have been proposed according to the study of the situation of the company and its commercial objectives.

Possibly one of the simplest and clearest may be the one proposed by Porter in 1986 and by Porter and Teece in 1992, with four general classic internationalization strategies.

Porter's simple export strategy locates production in a specific place from which production is exported to different destinations. This first option can be considered as an initial stage in the process of internationalization for manufacturing companies or with a strong physical component in the provision of services. A complex exporting strategy requires a marketing strategy with greater coordination (Porter, 1986). With this option, not only products and services are exported, but also an international marketing plan is developed considering at least the variables of product, price, place and promotion that make up the marketing-mix of the international offer.

On the other hand, as export activities are losing importance in favour of production in the destination markets, the multidomestic strategy emerges (Porter, 1986). This option involves the local production of products and services more adapted to the preferences and needs of each market. Although it is expected to generate greater value for local consumers, there might be a lack of coordination between the marketing management policies of the different subsidiaries. Many companies implement global strategies as they advance in their internationalization process and reach a higher degree of commitment to international markets (Porter, 1986). With this type of strategies, business management and marketing activities are strongly coordinated despite their application in widely dispersed geographical areas. A strategy applied globally allows us to offer a solid and robust international corporate image but can present problems if specific needs arise at a local level.

Keegan and Green (2017) propose the export selling strategy as a method that does not require the adaptation of marketing actions and can be useful for companies that start their export activity or for products and services with little competition in the new

markets. In the export marketing strategy, the four elements of marketing-mix are adapted as a result of the identification of different types of consumers in international markets. Comparing to Porter's strategies, export selling strategy would be similar to simple export, and export marketing strategy would be equivalent to complex export.

Porter's internationalization strategies are classified according to two dimensions, level of coordination and concentration of activities. Higher coordination of activities in complex export and global strategies, and less coordination in simple export and multidomestic. Higher level of concentration in simple and complex export, and lower concentration of actions in multidomestic and global strategies (Porter, 1986).

The four generic strategies and their two dimensions show the constant dilemma between standardization and adaptation of activities during the entire internationalization process. Obviously, the internationalization process, influenced by the reasons that cause it and the market entry methods, is the origin of this dilemma between standardization and adaptation of marketing policies, such as marketing-mix or international marketing communications. The reasons for internationalization will influence the choice of entry strategies, the evolution over time of these strategies, and the level of standardization or adaptation of marketing strategies.

Beyond the four basic and generic internationalization strategies described by Porter, other authors have advanced in the internationalization process by developing classifications of methods to enter new markets. These classifications have expanded the typology of export and FDI methods.

Based on the degree of involvement with the target market and the level of financial resources used, Keegan and Green (2017) propose a triple classification in exporting, licensing and investment. Another variable considered by these authors to increase the

level of involvement and financial resources in new markets is the level of experience obtained by the company through its international activities.

Export activities could be the first step of the internationalization process, requiring a low level of involvement and cost. Exporting may be an adequate response for companies that need rapid internationalization, as a consequence of competitors' movements (follow-the-competitor), clients' movements (follow-the-client), or the worsening of domestic market conditions. Exporting offers an agile response to these motivations of external and combined influence.

For firms that move forward in the process, licensing contracts would be an intermediate option between exporting and FDI. In licensing agreements, the licensor makes available to the licensee a legally protected asset in exchange for a compensation normally of an economic nature (Root, 2008). Within licensing options, we find two types, contract manufacturing and franchising (Keegan and Green, 2017). With contract manufacturing the international company provides technical indications of production to a local manufacturer, thus the licensor can focus on marketing activities and the licensee is the owner of the productive means and responsible for production in the local market. With franchising, the international company or franchiser gives to the local company or franchisee the right to operate a business model owned by the franchiser. The licensing, contract manufacturing and franchising options are especially suitable for internationalization processes motivated by the objective of increasing sales through the search for new markets, or the search for greater efficiency and economic profitability of existing assets (business model, products, brands, technical knowledge, etc.).

Investment would be the option that expresses the highest level of commitment to the new market, higher cost of activities, and greater accumulated international experience. Investment or FDI involve financial flows from the home country of the

international company to other countries for the construction or acquisition of productive assets or equity stakes (Root, 2008). Apart from the FDI in the construction of productive or commercial assets through own international subsidiaries, which would be one of the most advanced forms of internationalization, there are two forms of investment, the joint venture and total or partial acquisition of companies. In the joint venture the ownership of a new company is shared with a local partner. With the acquisition of shares, the international firm participates in the management of an existing organization in the target market (Keegan and Green, 2017). The use of the FDI options can respond to internal reasons for the search for new assets, resources and markets (Altzinger and Bellak, 1999), or the search for strategic leadership in the sector with large investments. As well as external reasons related to the structure of the new market or its access limitations.

West, Ford and Ibrahim (2015) propose a classification of foreign investment entry modes similar to that proposed by Keegan and Green (2017) with exporting, contractual arrangements, and FDI. They differentiate between indirect exporting for companies that export sporadically, and direct exporting for firms that need more control of frequent operations. Contractual arrangements would include licensing, franchising, and management, turnkey and manufacturing contracts. FDI operations would be the options of contractual and equity joint ventures, and wholly owned subsidiaries (Young, Hamill, Wheeler and Davis, 1989). Each of the strategies described would respond to a series of reasons depending on the situation and the environment of the organization, and its degree of internationalization.

2.3 Internationalization in context

Most publications and literature related to international marketing, international business and business internationalization do not address the question of why companies

decide to go to new foreign markets and expand their business in markets where they are new players and have to face new challenges related to different customers' needs and behaviours and new competitive environments. The reasons why companies go to international markets are scarcely exposed and explained in the existing literature. However, many textbooks and academic papers do address the issues of how these entry processes are carried out, and there is an extensive literature on typologies and classifications of internationalization strategies and methods of entry into new markets (Van Tulder, 2015).

We can also find extensive information on what products and services are subject to internationalization and what kind of adaptation processes are necessary for the offerings of the companies to be well received in the new destination markets. In summary, even though some authors have addressed the reasons for internationalization, the literature is scarce, not very exhaustive and widely disseminated. The most studied subjects on internationalization of companies have been which markets to enter, market entry strategies, how to do a global marketing plan and its implementation and control (Hollensen, 2017).

Studying the literature on business internationalization it seems that the motivation of companies for the growth and development of their business at an international level is something obvious (Van Tulder, 2015), as if that desire for growth were something natural and did not need explanation or classification, and the most important part was only how this process of international growth should take place. However, an adequate understanding of the reasons why organizations make international expansion decisions and what influences those decisions, would help to build better competitive strategies in international markets.

The initial literature that tried to explain the process of internationalization was based on marketing theories to which the specific components of foreign markets were added. As international trade and direct investment activities attracted more attention, several theories of internationalization were developed. Among the most relevant are the Uppsala model, transaction cost analysis model, Dunning's eclectic approach, network model, and more recently the born global model (Hollensen, 2017). All theories have had challenges in their practical application, have been criticized and extended by other authors, and have been challenged by new theories or later models.

The Uppsala model (Johanson and Wiedersheim-Paul, 1975) establishes a sequential and progressive model of four entry stages in foreign markets. Emphasizes the importance of gradually increasing commitment to the new market as experience is gained. In this model, two variables are very important, the level of commitment and the psychic distance determine the level of internationalization. This is one of the most popular and most reviewed and criticized models for its limited interpretation of the learning process and its difficulties to explain many other forms of internationalization (Forsgren, 2002). The Uppsala model does not reflect the great influence that some stakeholders have on the speed of the internationalization process (e.g. born globals). It also presents a reactive strategy -externally motivated- that is not in line with the active strategy -internally motivated- that many companies develop (Forsgren and Hagström, 2007).

The transaction cost model (Buckley and Casson, 1976; Buckley and Casson, 2003) establishes a dichotomy between the concepts of externalization and internalization. When it comes to internationalization, the company must decide between a firm-based internal method (e.g., own subsidiary) or do so through a market-based external solution (e.g. collaboration with an external partner).

Eclectic framework (Dunning, 2016) proposes that a company is willing to internationalize its activities if the ownership, locational, and internalization advantages are satisfied. This framework focus on the importance of locational factors.

The network model (Johanson and Mattsson, 2015; Hood and Vahlne, 2013) proposes that companies cannot be studied in isolation. Companies are part of an international network in which they are affected by the situations or decisions of other players. This network can be used as a method of entry to other markets based on personal relations.

Born globals are companies that do not follow a traditional process on their way to international markets. These are companies that since its creation have as a target the global market without the need to work in their local market or develop a prolonged process of internationalization (Gabrielsson and Kirpalani, 2004). They are usually companies with high technological component or that work in sectors in which the technology allows a complete development of the business without location barriers. They can apply their business model quickly in any market (Hollensen, 2017).

This paper does not intend to study internationalization theories or entry methods, but it is useful to expose some of them briefly, to demonstrate that factors that motivate and influence internationalization are very numerous. The creation and evolution of internationalization theories and entry methods are a direct consequence of the complexity and the growing number of factors that affect the reasons for the internationalization of firms.

The theories of internationalization exposed reflect some internal motives that drive companies towards new markets, and which are related to factors of commitment of the company with the target market and psychological distance (Uppsala), organic growth versus growth with partners (transaction), and ownership, location and competitive

advantages (Dunning's). External reasons can be seen influenced by the interaction of companies with their environment (network), and reasons of mixed nature influenced by technological advances and the company's own capabilities (born globals).

2.4 Internationalization is strategy

Internationalization is a field of study that belongs to strategic marketing and strategic management. The international business process will always involve the cycle of analysis, decision making, implementation of strategies and control of metrics within an international environment, that is, Where are we now? -audit phase-, Where do we want to be? -strategy phase-, How will we get there? -translation phase-, and Did we get there? -evaluation phase- (West *et al.*, 2015). As part of strategic marketing, the complete cycle of internationalization will always follow the three areas of strategic marketing management, namely, strategic analysis, strategic choice, and strategic implementation (Johnson, Scholes and Whittington, 2009).

FIGURE 1
Areas of strategic marketing management

Johnson, Scholes and Whittington, 2009

Strategic choice consists of the process by which a decision is made among several possible alternatives considering the orientation and competitive advantage of the

company, and the direction and method of development. For example, in this phase it would be decided which are the target markets of internationalization, what kind of products or services are going to be offered in the new markets, or what level of standardization or adaptation will be chosen considering the encouraging factors for each option (Czinkota, Ronkainen and Zvobgo, 2011; Hollensen, 2017).

Strategic implementation is the process that puts into practice the plans and actions. It describes the processes and steps that must be followed to achieve the objectives of the plan. Ultimately, it is a tactical plan that establishes the key success factors, the organizational structure, the leadership style and the corporate culture that will be applied in the operational development of the plan. In this phase the entry methods and management orientations -ethnocentric, polycentric, regiocentric and geocentric- would be developed, the necessary investments would be made, and the global marketing plan would be designed and implemented (Keegan and Schlegelmilch, 2001; Hollensen, 2017).

But it is the first of the three areas mentioned above, strategic analysis, the one with higher importance when discussing the reasons that lead companies to decide to enter new international markets. The strategic analysis considers the different environments that influence the competitive dynamics of companies. These are the internal environment, the competitive environment or microenvironment, and the macroenvironment. Strategic analysis “is concerned with understanding the position of the organisation in terms of its external environment, internal resources and competencies” (Johnson *et al.*, 2009).

Considering internationalization as part of the business strategy, and considering the components of strategic analysis, we can already propose a group of sources of reasons for companies to make strategic moves in other countries. These factors would

have their origin in the different environments that make up the firm's marketing environment. The reasons for internationalization would have as influence what happens inside the company, in its competitive microenvironment, and in its macroenvironment, that is, reasons caused by internal factors, factors of the closest competitive environment, and external factors.

According to the marketing environment proposed by West *et al.* (2015), internal factors emanate from the company; people who compose it, their relationships, its structure, and the management style. The value chain (Porter, 1998) is one of the tools used for internal analysis. The microenvironment is made up of the company's relationship with its competitors, customers, suppliers and distributors. A popular microenvironment study tool would be Porter's five forces (2008). The macroenvironment is composed of political, economic, sociocultural, technological, legal, and environmental factors -PESTLE analysis- (West *et al.*, 2015). Some authors extend it with ethical and demographic factors -STEEPLED analysis- (Sammut-Bonnici and Galea, 2015).

FIGURE 2
The marketing environment

West, Ford and Ibrahim (2015)

Yip (2003) establishes four drivers to decide about the internationalization strategy of a firm: market, government, competitive and cost drivers. The internationalization strategy would be selected considering company's objectives, its products or services, and the drivers. Market drivers would involve the need for potential customers and the global marketing strategy. Government drivers would be trade policies, technical standards, protectionist barriers, and government policies related to international trade. Competitors' global strategies and trade relationship between the countries would be part of competitive drivers. Cost drivers would be influenced by economies of scale, geographical advantages and other factors such as logistics. Once again, using Yip's framework is possible to highlight the presence of internal factors (cost), external factors (government), and mixed factors (market and competition) when it comes to make internationalization decisions.

2.5 Importance of internationalization reasons

Some famous internationalization theories have been reviewed for their limits of application beyond the framework in which they were conceived. For example, the Uppsala model explained how companies gradually internationalized as their knowledge and commitment to new markets increased. But as business environment becomes more complex and more factors must be considered, some theories are not applicable because they show a limited view of the business environment. Everything that happens inside and outside the company influences business decisions. Internationalization theories would be much more realistic and applicable if they considered motivational factors.

Therefore, it can be said that internationalization theories and entry methods are a direct consequence of the strategic decisions, and the strategy is determined by the

different reasons that shape it. A good knowledge of these reasons would help to build a more accurate and adequate international strategy.

In order to truly understand the internationalization process, relations among its components must be established. Benito (2015) relates the reasons to the “where” and “how” and the internationalization theories, establishing the relationship of the reasons with the selection of international markets, the entry methods, and the theoretical aspects.

The review of the literature on internationalization shows that it has been putting the cart before the horse. Theories have been developed and entry methods studied without paying true attention to what motivates the entire process.

Several reasons and classifications have been proposed (Cuervo-Cazurra and Narula, 2015) but only Dunning’s theoretical framework (1993) has had real influence in the study of motives and has only done it partially. It has not been until the Reading-UNCTAD International Business Conference in April 2013 on contemporary issues in international business theory, that several authors have developed some conceptual papers about the variety of motives and the most prominent classifications creating a debate in *Multinational Business Review* (Cuervo-Cazurra and Narula, 2015; Benito, 2015; Cuervo-Cazurra *et al.*, 2015; Van Tulder, 2015). Nor have the reasons that drive companies to internationalize in a specific geographical and time frames have not been studied.

According to Van Tulder (2015) the research gap to explain the original motives of companies to carry out international business actions “can be partly explained by methodological difficulties in getting representative managers to reveal their real motives to move abroad through surveys and interviews”, also by “theoretical fragmentation”, and “lack of sophistication in the adoption of analytical frameworks.”

Some literature (Peng, 2004; Cuervo-Cazurra and Narula, 2015; Van Tulder, 2015) suggests that managers and executives have difficulties when articulating the real reasons to expand their commercial and production activities to new international markets. The reasons why business managers do not know, cannot or do not want to express clearly those reasons can be diverse. Firstly, the complexity of business management means that decisions of the Management are influenced by innumerable factors of different origins. When it comes to finding a set of clear reasons that explain why to expand business into new markets, it is difficult to identify clear and precise points on which to base decisions. Secondly, there may be situations where managers cannot recognize why certain decisions are exactly made. Current competitive environment of companies is changing and complicated, and it may be the case that managers justify their decisions using inaccurate reasons. For example, a manager may justify entering a new market by looking for an increase in the number of clients and volume of sales, when in reality his/her decision could be influenced by the international expansion of competitors. In this case, the company may feel forced to compete in new markets if it does not want to lose competitiveness that could also later affect it negatively in its own local market. It can also be the case that it is justified as a decision that is part of the company's competitive strategy, when possibly they are just taking advantage of an unexpected commercial opportunity in a new market that was not part of the company's plans.

These are just examples of the difficulties that can arise when trying to establish the true reasons for certain business decisions. But the identification of the true reasons for internationalization would help companies to better understand their competitive environment and achieve better results in international markets through much more adequate internationalization strategies. From the point of view of the managerial implications, knowing the real reasons why companies initiate and develop international

activities would help in their decision-making process, and especially in their decisions on how to enter a new market and how to face the rivalry with local and international competitors.

From a theoretical point of view, Benito (2015) proposes that knowledge of reasons for internationalization has two advantages. The reasons that drive international business are “associated with central aspects of internationalization” that makes them “relevant variables” when studying the processes of internationalization of companies. And, these motives “serve as key markers for the conceptual domains of (internationalization) theories.”

Therefore, from a managerial point of view the study of reasons for internationalization would serve as tools to design better competitive strategies based on a deep knowledge of the reality of the company and its environment. From a theoretical point of view, the study of these motivations contributes to the development of stronger theories and are factors that allow a better study and understanding of the complete internationalization process.

2.6 Reasons for internationalization

Despite the lack of exhaustive studies on the reasons for internationalization, some authors have proposed, in a more or less solid way and in different degrees of depth, typologies of motives to address export actions and direct investment in other markets.

Dunning (1993) proposed a conceptual framework that groups together four main motives composed of resource-, market-, efficiency-, and asset-seeking. According to Canals (1994) the main reasons for internationalization were the opening of new markets, obtaining lower production costs, and greater efficiency in production and distribution structures. Dicken (2003) mentioned the economic profit as the most important motive,

and secondarily others such as increasing the market share, being the industry leader, and increasing the size of the company. Daniels, Radebaugh and Sullivan (2005) exposed more vaguely about reasons for increasing sales, reducing risk and acquiring resources, among other secondary reasons for internationalization. Rugman and Collinson (2006) do not propose an exhaustive classification but several practical reasons, such as following competitors' steps to avoid losing competitiveness, reducing costs through, for example, economies of scale, expanding and exploiting in more markets the technological knowledge generated in the local market, and reduce risks by diversifying markets to protect the organization from the economic cycles of the domestic market.

Czinkota, Ronkainen, Moffett, Marinova and Marinov (2009) propose a bipolar classification with proactive reasons, those that are born directly from the Management of the company in search of objectives marked from within the organization, and reactive reasons, which would be those motivated by movements of external players or caused by situations outside the company.

Lee and Carter (2012) highlight risk diversification as a reason for internationalization. Navarro-García *et al.* (2015) in their study on the determinants of export distinguish between internal and external factors. The internal determining factors are based on the resource-based view and would be those related to the organizational resources and capabilities of the company. The personal characteristics of the people who decide on export and internationalization actions, such as their commitment to the company's export and international strategic vision, would also be part of this group. For the determinants of external type, these authors use the contingency approach, classifying them into two groups. These factors would be related to the environment of the company, either with its local or international environments, and considering the distance between markets, and the environment of the industry, considering the competitive intensity within

the sector. Cuervo-Cazurra *et al.* (2015) propose sell more, buy better, upgrade and escape as a result of exploitation and exploration of existing and new resources, and the search for better conditions related to home- and host-country factors.

Due to the complexity of the internationalization process and the different influences, business decisions may be based on a “combination of motives” (Benito, 2015) and not on a single type of reasons. Gillespie and Hennessey (2015) propose obtaining profitability, but also highlight getting new knowledge. They also consider as a reason for internationalization the public programs for the promotion of exports developed by governments.

Pederzoli and Kuppelwieser (2015) proposed that the international strategy may change “due to several micro- and macro-environmental reasons”. They also talked about “push” and “pull” factors to explain the reasons for the increase of international activity during the 2008 crisis of companies in the retail sector. We could match the push and pull factors to the proactive and reactive reasons of Czinkota *et al.* (2009). As suggested in this paper, Pederzoli and Kuppelwieser refer to micro- and macro-environmental changes that influence internationalization decisions and strategies.

Van Tulder (2015) groups the reasons for internationalization. Intrinsic reasons refer the advantages of working in international markets and the efficiency of managing resources internationally. These would correspond to Dunning’s motives. Extrinsic reasons are related to conditions in the domestic and in the new destination markets. Finally, mixed reasons combine intrinsic and extrinsic to form a category that reflects the influences of the competitive structure of the industry or sector to which the company belongs.

Among the reasons proposed by Azuayi (2016) are saturated local markets and working in markets with higher growth rates. Hollensen (2017) refers to “make money”

and “mixture of factors” as reasons to export. Hollensen and Arteaga (2010) also follow the classification of Czinkota *et al.* (2009). Proactive reasons would affect strategy, internal competencies and market perception, such as managerial issues, growth and profit objectives, or product advantages. Reactive reasons appear when companies do not develop changes in their strategy but adapt to changes in the environment related to competitors’ movements, local market situation, or unexpected international opportunities.

Garzón Osorio (2018) proposes the classification of endogenous and exogenous factors, but in this case referring not to the reasons for internationalization, but for the opposite process, the de-internationalization or withdrawal of international markets in which the firm had previously invested.

After reviewing the literature related to important aspects of the internationalization process and business strategy that may affect internationalization, together with a comprehensive review of the most important and current classifications of internationalization reasons, we can see several common factors.

When we cross the literature on strategy and on internationalization reasons, we see that there are three scenarios that coincide. The environments that condition the business strategy are the same that group the different types of reasons for internationalization.

FIGURE 3
Company environment and internationalization reasons

Drawn by the author

2.6.1 Internal reasons

The company itself is where what authors name as internal, intrinsic, proactive, push or endogenous factors come from. They are the company's own decisions derived from the entrepreneurial or leadership nature and the strategic vision of the Management, also from specific company's factors or needs.

Dunning (1993) and Dunning and Narula (1995) proposed a series of reasons encompassed in the concept of "locational advantages" creating a theoretical framework with four internal reasons why companies can be motivated to develop activities outside their borders, more specifically to make commercial and productive investments abroad.

Dunning's resource-seeking reasons refer to the availability of natural resources, infrastructure, and more economical workforce or with adequate skills to perform commercial or productive tasks. These are reasons why companies can be encouraged to carry out internationalization activities. Market-seeking is when certain countries can be attractive due to the size of their market, their economic growth rate, or per capita income level. New markets with these characteristics are a claim for companies in growth process because of the economic opportunities they offer. With efficiency-seeking international companies seek to make the best possible use of its resources, systems, processes, and commercial and productive structures to increase its level of efficiency by locating its activities in strategically suitable locations. Asset-seeking occurs when a company acquires assets in other countries aiming to improve its capabilities both nationally and internationally (Meyer, 2015). The assets acquired can be of any kind, from a brand, a business model, productive capacities to a full company.

The reasons proposed by Dunning would not be a complete framework, since they presuppose that the management of the company has a proactive strategic approach and does not consider the reasons of defensive type influenced by players or existing

situations in the environment (Benito, 2015). This classification does not consider the external dimension and many elements of the company's environment (Meyer, 2015; Cuervo-Cazurra and Narula, 2015), but it is totally valid from an internal point of view.

Internal reasons are those that arise from the company's need for new resources, market expansion, improvement of efficiencies and new assets. They are related to the capabilities and resources of the company, its availability and sufficiency. They are also related to weaknesses and strengths, and the international strategy to correct weaknesses and take advantage of strengths. Internal motivations of the company to carry out internationalization and FDI activities proposed by Dunning, have been widely recognized by many authors as a solid and useful framework to analyze the international business development strategies that have been carried out in recent years (Ivarsson and Jonsson, 2003; Makino, Lau and Yeh, 2002; Verbeke, 2013). According to this framework, we can predict a significant relationship between the specific internal factors of the firm and the importance and development of internationalization activities:

H1: There is a significant relationship between the specific internal factors of the firm and the development of internationalization activities.

2.6.2 External reasons

Using Dunning's factors as a basis, Cuervo-Cazurra and Narula (2015) establish that it would not be theoretically correct to use them as main or "primary" motives and leave other types of motives as "secondary". We can conclude that, although studies have focused on internal reasons (Van Tulder, 2015), there are also other types of factors of external origin of equal importance and great complexity.

The macroenvironment is the source from which external, extrinsic, reactive, pull or exogenous factors come. These are factors that can affect any player in a given

environment, including the economy, sector or industry as a whole, and the company has a limited ability to influence them. They are threats or opportunities that occur both in the domestic and international markets. The company must adapt to these changes or generate an appropriate strategy that allows to minimize threats and take advantage of opportunities. Factors of external origin that influence the motivations for internationalization are included in the PESTLE or STEEPLED analyses and can occur both in the domestic or international markets where the firm is operating.

The importance of external reasons is that they can arise from various environments -local or foreign- and are diverse in nature -political, legal, ethical, economic, social, demographic, technological or environmental-. Van Tulder (2015) divides these reasons into home- and host-country dimensions, and relates them to risk diversification and escape reasons in search of better conditions abroad or avoiding negative situations in the domestic market. According to these dimensions, we can predict a relationship between the external factors and the importance and development of internationalization activities by firms:

H2: There is a significant relationship between the home-country related factors and the development of internationalization activities.

H3: There is a significant relationship between the host-country related factors and the development of internationalization activities.

2.6.3 Mixed or combined reasons

The microenvironment is the source from which combined reasons or mixture of reasons come. This category includes factors that have a combined origin, factors that have internal and external origin. They are external factors to the company, but at the same time internal to the sector, industry or direct competitive environment in which the

firm develops its productive or commercial activity. Some authors refer to these motivational factors as “sector intrinsic motives” (Slager, 2004; Van Tulder, 2015) or as factors of the “environment of the industry” (Navarro-García *et al.*, 2015) because they affect the competitive structure of a certain sector.

They are reasons related to the closest and most direct environment of the company, and mainly arise from the company’s relationship with its competitors and customers. Among the clients we can consider not only the final customers of products and services (business-to-consumer, B2C), but also intermediate clients such as distributors and professional or institutional clients (business-to-business, B2B).

Van Tulder (2015) relates these types of reasons with the competitive intensity of the sector and how the company’s experience in the local market affects its international potential. This author also introduces the psychological factors that make companies imitate or replicate in some way the international operations of their competitors (follow-the-competitor reasons), and the reasons why companies develop activities to meet the needs of their current clients in new international markets (follow-the-client reasons). According to these motivations, we can predict a relationship between the mixed factors and the importance and development of internationalization activities by firms:

H4: There is a significant relationship between the follow-the-competitor related factors and the development of internationalization activities.

H5: There is a significant relationship between the follow-the-client related factors and the development of internationalization activities.

2.6.4 2008 crisis and public programs to promote internationalization

This research uses companies from the Spanish region of Andalusia as a study framework. In recent years Andalusia has experienced a significant increase in its exports

and internationalization of its companies. From 2009 to 2017, exports increased from 9.89% to 19.92% of Andalusian GDP, reaching 30,913 million euros and 24,107 exporting companies (Datosmarco Expansión, 2019; Extenda, 2019). Andalusia has gone from a structural deficit to having three consecutive years of international trade surplus from (2016 - 2018). Exports in the region grew twice as much as in Spain and in most OECD countries in 2017. In 2018 it was the region that contributed most to the export growth of Spain (Revista APD, 2018).

In Spain as a whole, exports have grown at high rates, Spanish investment abroad has grown steadily from 2009 to 2017, and the weight of the foreign economic sector in Spain increased to 33.1% of GDP in 2016 (Instituto de Empresa Familiar, 2012; Ministerio de Economía, Industria y Competitividad, 2017).

In the internationalization of Andalusian and Spanish companies in recent years there have been two specific and notable factors that may have influenced their internationalization process: the global economic and financial crisis that began in 2008 and the proliferation of public programs to support exports and internationalization. Both could be classified as external factors that affect internationalization decisions from the double dimension of home- and host-country factors, since they affect the macroeconomic conditions of both the domestic and international markets.

The crisis that began in 2008 caused virtually all advanced economies to enter recession (United Nations, 2012). The plight of financial institutions and the complicated access to financing since 2008 led to a reduction in international trade flows (Chor and Manova, 2012). Flows related to internationalization of companies are always affected when an economic, financial or political crisis arises, since companies are increasingly exposed to experience the consequences of crises that arise in other places (Arteaga Ortiz, 2017).

In addition, because of the effects of the crises, the inverse process of internationalization occurs. Withdrawal of companies from foreign markets in which they had previously established, either totally or partially (Garzón Osorio, 2018). Examples are the “de-internationalization” of banking institutions after the beginning of the crisis in 2008 (Van Tulder, 2015).

Despite the negative effects of the crisis, in recent years the activities of internationalization of Andalusian companies have been much stronger and more decisive than in previous periods (Pérez-Suárez and Bustelo, 2014). During the crisis, many Spanish companies have found in exports the solution to the drop in the demand of the domestic market, seeking new clients and greater economic margins in the international markets (Giménez, 2010). Regarding the international retail sector, Pederzoli and Kuppelwieser (2015) found that the international activities of these companies increased after the 2008 crisis, both in volume of operations and in the number of companies involved. According to this scenario, we can predict a relationship between the 2008 economic-financial crisis and its consequences, and the development of internationalization activities by firms:

H6: There is a significant relationship between the consequences of the 2008 economic-financial crisis and the development of internationalization activities.

Activity in the area of internationalization has been driven from several points of interest. According to Welch and Luostarinen (1988), it has been companies for their concern to carry out their international activity more efficiently in a highly competitive environment. But also, from governments that have tried to ensure that the process of internationalization of their companies has positive effects in the economic interests of the country or region.

Prowse (2002) recognizes the role of governmental institutions that establish adequate trade policies and reforms as a way to develop the country within a global context.

Porter (2011) defines four factors that make countries more competitive -diamond model- which are: firm strategy, structure and rivalry; factor conditions; demand conditions; and related and supporting industries. Additionally, he defines two external factors that influence the model: causality and government. Causality refers to external and out of control events for companies and governments. Government groups together all the policies that favour the competitiveness of domestic firms, such as programs to support and promote exports and internationalization.

There are companies that decide to export to take advantage of public incentives (Azuayi, 2016). Keegan and Green (2017) define tax incentives, free trade zones, subsidies, and governmental assistance to exporters as forms of government programs to promote exports. Export assistance consists of actions to promote exports, trade missions and participation in fairs to increase international sales, and facilitate education and information on new markets and risks. Gillespie and Hennessey (2015) stress that many companies have been able to access international markets thanks to public programs.

Supporting the internationalization of companies has been a priority for Spanish public institutions. Internationalization support programs have provided large financial resources with annual budgets of more than 1,200 million euros (Instituto de Empresa Familiar, 2012). Cansino *et al.* (2013) evaluate the effectiveness of public programs to initiate the internationalization of Andalusian companies and conclude that they are “an effective tool to promote internationalization” and “to increase exports”. According to this, we can predict a relationship between the public programs to support exports and internationalization, and the development of internationalization activities by firms:

H7: There is a significant relationship between the public programs to support exports and internationalization and the development of internationalization activities.

3. Model

Following the conclusions drawn from the review of the literature, following the holistic framework proposed by Van Tulder (2015) that groups and classifies the reasons for internationalization, and including two specific factors related to the internationalization of Spanish companies in recent years backed by literature, the proposed model is represented in Figure 2.

The difficulty of designing a model that explains the reasons for internationalization should be highlighted since there could be multiple (Benito, 2015), the absence of a “sophisticated” investigation (Van Tulder, 2015), and it’s “somewhat atheoretical” and has value “when used in conjunction with other frameworks” (Cuervo-Cazurra and Narula, 2015).

The results of internationalization can be measured in economic terms, growth, learning and innovation, reduction of risk, and achievement of strategic objectives. To assess the perspectives, the relationship between the internationalization process and the achievement of growth and strategic development are included in the model. The rest of the potential results have been discarded due to their measurement complexity and for being out of the purpose and scope of this study.

H8: There is a significant relationship between the development of internationalization activities and the achievement of business growth.

H9: There is a significant relationship between the development of internationalization activities and the strategic performance.

FIGURE 4
Proposed Model

Drawn by the author

4. Methodology

4.1 Sampling frame

The questionnaire was sent to CEOs, export managers, international marketing managers and international business development managers of companies with headquarters in Andalusia.

The directory of Andalusian exporting companies prepared annually by Andalucía Económica magazine -edition 321 of June 15, 2019, paper format- was used (Appendix 3). This publication collects export data and contact information voluntarily delivered by 300 companies. The publication lists companies by export volume from 926 million to 3 million euros. Although the magazine calls it “export ranking”, the directory actually includes companies that carry out exporting and FDI activities. Seven companies were discarded for having their headquarters outside Andalusia. Companies with a generic contact email (e.g. info@example.com, contact@example.com) were contacted through the professional social network LinkedIn.

This directory is especially valid and useful as companies that have developed internationalization activities in recent years were needed and this directory includes exclusively exporting and internationalized companies.

4.2 Survey instrument

Based on the literature review and the conceptual framework, an online questionnaire on Qualtrics containing 30 questions was developed.

Four versions of the questionnaire were pretested with three professionals with internationalization knowledge in order to assess adequacy of the duration, understanding

of the questions and vocabulary used. The online questionnaire, introduction letter and instructions were sent to firms in the local language (Spanish).

The model constructs were assessed on a multi-item five-point Likert scale which allows the use of multiple regression analysis. The annual total sales, number of countries with operations, and percentages of sales and employees in international markets were assessed on ordinal scale only with the purpose of classification. Other questions were established on nominal scale only with the purpose of analyzing frequencies for additional information, not as part of the main constructs.

The set of internal factors have been evaluated as a whole, due to the complexity to measure them individually and the generalized executives' need for further explanation about them in the pretested questionnaires. Analysis of individual internal factors has been done by frequency distribution. The influence of internationalization on growth and strategic performance has been assessed through linear correlation analysis.

4.3 Data collection

The questionnaire link was sent to 334 executives from 293 companies. 121 responses were recorded on Qualtrics, 89 of them were completed correctly, valid and usable. The valid response rate was 26.7%.

5. Findings and analysis

Tables 1, 2 and 3 show the summary of the main results of the study. The study framework were the Andalusian companies that have developed internationalization activities, and the time frame they were asked is during the last ten years. Period in which there has been a significant increase in international activities of Andalusian firms. All estimates were made at a level of confidence of 0.95 (significance level $\alpha = 0.05$).

5.1 Hypothesis 1: Internal reasons

With *p-value* 0.011 and *t Stat* 2.605 for internal factors, we can say that H1 is supported. Therefore, there is a statistically significant relationship between the specific internal motivational factors of the firm and the development of internationalization activities. One of the characteristics that companies with strong internal, proactive or push motivations show is their willingness to be a prominent player in their sectors. 68.5% of respondents stated that they always sought to be leaders in the markets in which they operate. Among the classic set of internal reasons, it should be noted that 80.9% of respondents indicated that market-seeking was the main internal reason for internationalization, followed by efficiency-seeking (15.7%). We can conclude that internal reasons, specific to the structure of the company and the strategic vision of the Management have influenced the internationalization process of Andalusian companies, and that the search for new markets and customers has been the main internal reason.

5.2 Hypotheses 2 and 3: External reasons

With *p-value* 0.008 and *t Stat* -2.698 for home-country factors, and *p-value* 0.272 and *t Stat* 1.105 for host-country factors, we can say that H2 is supported, and H3 is not.

Therefore, of the external motivational factors, there is a statistically significant relationship between the factors related to the situation of the domestic market and the development of internationalization activities, while this is not the case for factors related to the conditions of foreign markets. 58.4% of respondents indicated that their companies have internationalized because the domestic market did not offer real growth opportunities. We can conclude that among the external reasons the situation of the domestic market has influenced the internationalization of Andalusian companies, while the conditions or opportunities in foreign markets are not statistically significant.

5.3 Hypotheses 4 and 5: Mixed or combined reasons

With *p-value* 0.491 and *t Stat* -0.692 for the follow-the-competitor factors, and a *p-value* 0.028 and *t Stat* 2.233 for the follow-the-client factors, we can say that H4 is not supported, while H5 is supported. Therefore, of the mixed motivational factors, there is a statistically significant relationship between the factors related to the movements of clients and the development of internationalization activities, while this is not the case for the factors related to the movements of competitors. 53.9% of respondents indicated that their companies have internationalized following the steps or needs of their customers. 58.4% of respondents stated that their companies have not internationalized following the example or steps of their competitors. We can conclude that among the mixed or combined reasons, client movements have influenced the internationalization of Andalusian companies, while competitor movements were not statistically significant.

5.4 Hypotheses 6 and 7: 2008 crisis and public programs to promote internationalization

With *p-value* 0.403 and *t-Stat* 0.893 for the influence of the 2008 crisis, and *p-value* 0.328 and *t-Stat* -0.983 for the influence of public programs to promote exports and FDI, we can say that H6 and H7 are not supported. Therefore, of the external factors added to the model due to their importance in the internationalization of Spanish companies in recent years, neither the crisis of 2008 nor the public programs to support internationalization have had a statistically significant effect on the development of internationalization activities.

TABLE 1
Descriptive Statistics

Multiple Regression Analysis

Constructs	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
<i>External factors</i>				
Home-country	- 0.222	0.082	- 2.698	0.008
Host-country	0.143	0.129	1.105	0.272
2008 crisis	0.062	0.074	0.893	0.403
Public programs	- 0.064	0.065	- 0.983	0.328
<i>Mixed or combined factors</i>				
Follow-the-competitor	- 0.051	0.073	- 0.692	0.491
Follow-the-client	0.142	0.063	2.233	0.028
<i>Internal factors</i>				
	0.197	0.075	2.605	0.011

TABLE 2
Frequency Distribution of Internal Factors

Resources-seeking	Market-seeking	Efficiency-seeking	Asset-seeking	Other motives	Total
0	80.9	15.7	0	3.4	100

5.5 Hypotheses 8 and 9: Growth and strategic performance

Regarding internationalization activities and their effect on the results of business growth and achievement of strategic objectives, there is a low positive correlation with growth ($r = 0.154$), and a moderate positive correlation with strategic performance ($r = 0.316$).

TABLE 3
Descriptive Statistics

Linear correlation analysis	
<i>Internationalization activities</i>	
<i>Growth</i>	0.154
<i>Strategic performance</i>	0.316

FIGURE 5
Proposed model and results (Multiple regression analysis)

* Linear correlation analysis

6. Discussion

This research offers a useful conceptual classification of the reasons for internationalization based on Van Tulder's approach (2015). This study covers the gap in the literature by applying these reasons in an empirical way in specific time and geographical framework -Andalusia in the last decade-. There was no study that applied existing classifications and investigated these motivations with companies from a specific region and during a given period.

The literature pointed out that although many executives tend to simplify the reasons for internationalization (Van Tulder, 2015), even many professionals often indicate unique reasons that prevail over others, actually companies develop internationalization processes motivated by multiple reasons (Lee and Carter, 2012; Benito, 2015; Pederzoli and Kuppelwieser, 2015). After analyzing the proposed model we can conclude that, in the case of the companies studied, this multiplicity of reasons is fulfilled.

Consistent with Van Tulder's proposition, the internationalization activities of these companies have been motivated by internal reasons, mainly by the search for new markets and customers. For external reasons, the situation in the domestic market has influenced their decision to enter foreign markets. And for combined reasons, since they have followed the steps and needs of their clients in the new markets.

Although the most recent literature recognizes the relevance of all types of motivational factors, some studies on internationalization show a certain prevalence of internal reasons over other reasons (Dunning, 1993; Dicken, 2003; Cuervo-Cazurra and Narula, 2015). This occurs mainly for two reasons. Early studies in this field focused on internal motivational factors. And secondly, executives tend to justify their decisions

from their own point of view, from their own influence on decisions. Therefore, it would be logical that when executives are asked about reasons to go to international markets, the internal reasons were relevant. This study shows that internal factors are not the only ones, but they are significant and have influenced the internationalization process according to respondents.

The analysis also demonstrates the relevance of the external motivational factors found in the literature, specifically the domestic market situation of the companies surveyed has influenced their decision to address new international markets. The literature indicates some barriers that prevent the growth of companies in their domestic markets, such as saturated markets, high level of competition, having already reached a remarkable market share, or an adverse economic or legal situation (Giménez, 2010; Azuayi, 2016).

Despite what indicated in the literature, the conditions of foreign markets have not been significant. But this does not mean that companies ignore the situation in the target markets. Probably the situation of the domestic market is one of the initial factors that first drive the internationalization process, to later evaluate the attractiveness of foreign markets. In fact, in the executives' mindset the opportunities offered by international markets were very relevant when asked using a nominal scale (Appendix 4, Table 4).

This study also demonstrates the relevance of the combined reasons. In the case of the companies studied, their internationalization has not been influenced by competitors' behaviour, but by the needs of their clients in other markets. This may be due to the composition of the sample. Many of the companies that make up the directory belong to the B2B sector, and these companies are more likely to follow the movements of their clients since they could be suppliers of companies that have also internationalized. When asked using a nominal scale, respondents clearly expressed that they did not follow the

steps of their competitors (Appendix 4, Table 4). In the case of clients movements, although in nominal scale their frequency was also very low, when using a Likert scale and regression analysis the variable was clearly significant.

Although the literature suggested that economic crises and public programs could influence internationalization decisions, this has not been fulfilled in the case of the companies analysed. The frequency of these two variables asked in nominal scale has been very low, and using Likert scale and regression analysis, their significance has been definitively discarded.

However, when asked about the internationalization of Andalusian companies in general, 82% of respondents indicated that 2008 crisis influenced and boosted their internationalization. When asking about the usefulness of public internationalization support programs, 84.3% of respondents said they were useful, and 74.2% responded affirmatively when asked if public programs have influenced the internationalization of Andalusian companies. According to these data, executives tend to recognize the influence of the crisis and public programs in the business sector as a whole to a greater extent than when they are asked about the influence of these same factors on the internationalization of their own companies (Appendix 4, Tables 5 and 6).

Regarding the influence of internationalization on growth and strategic performance, we see a low and moderate linear correlation respectively. This could be interpreted as internationalization activities influence business growth and strategic performance, but in the executives' mindset it is not the only factor, nor the main factor, that affects these variables. Possibly, executives believe that growth and strategic performance are influenced by more factors besides internationalization activities.

These findings partly support previous studies, since some of the reasons for internationalization have been significant while others have not. What has been clearly

demonstrated is the influence of multiple factors of all company environments -firm itself, microenvironment and macroenvironment- in the internationalization process.

7. Conclusion and managerial recommendations

Companies must be aware of the multiple reasons that motivate their decisions in order to design an international strategy that is truly appropriate to the environments in which they operate. This variety of motivational factors will influence the selection of new markets, the design of the marketing-mix, and the selection of entry modes, as well as the subsequent strategic adjustments in any part of the process.

The strategic analysis together with the study of the reasons for internationalization allows to determine the environment from which they come. The determination of the competitive factors that influence and motivate internationalization enables the design of a strategy fully adapted to the competitive environment of each company.

The knowledge of the factors that motivate internationalization will influence the success or failure of the international strategy. Successful internationalization strategies will be those based on the real knowledge of the motivational factors since they will adapt better to the company's environment.

This research demonstrates the multiple origin of motivational factors. Therefore, executives must broaden their vision of the competitive environment and recognize the true sources from which these factors come. Thus, they would avoid the tendency to justify their decisions from an internal point of view that can lead them to design inaccurate strategies.

The analysis of the reasons for internationalization acquires true meaning and utility when used in conjunction with other studies. The analysis of reasons should serve as the basis on which to build internationalization theories and design entry modes.

International strategies should always be tailor-made. But companies that are in a similar environment to that found by Andalusian companies in recent years, can use the

results of this study to consider internal factors, situation of the domestic market and movements of clients as relevant factors.

The influence of government programs has not been significant, may be because these programs do not adapt to the real needs of companies. The results of this study can contribute to designing internationalization support programs that are much more adapted to the real motivational factors of companies.

2008 crisis has not been significant, but to the extent that it could have affected the domestic market situation, it could be considered as potentially influential. To find it out another study would be necessary.

8. Limitations and future research

Given the size and composition of the database used, conclusions should be considered with restraint. It is difficult to prepare a questionnaire that contains theoretical concepts and that at the same time is completely understandable by executives who are accustomed to practical concepts. Many executives do not know the true reasons for internationalization of their companies, they only know them partially, or they do not properly discern between internal or external reasons. There is also a tendency for executives to integrate external influences as part of their internal logical reasoning.

The group of internationalized Andalusian companies is largely made up of companies in the B2B sector. This is not a limitation, but conditions the generalization of the results. It would be interesting to study the motivations for internationalization distinguishing between B2B and B2C companies, since their strategic dynamics may differ. This comparative study would be useful especially for microenvironment reasons related to the movements of competitors and customers.

This paper opens several possibilities for new researches. It would be interesting to study which specific subfactors of the significant reasons of this paper are those that drive internationalization with a highest level of accuracy. Subfactors from the internal environment -company structure, management style, international experience, etc.-; from the domestic market -size, competition, market share, economic situation, etc.-; and from clients' movements -bargaining power, client dependency, pulling power, vertical integration potential, etc.-.

This research studies the internationalization of Andalusian companies. To draw more generalizable conclusions, it would be interesting to make a comparative study with companies from more regions or countries in the same period or under similar

environmental conditions. Thus, it could be concluded if there are any differences or similarities in the reasons that motivate internationalization.

Appendices

Appendix 1. Ethics approval letter

Research Ethics
Office

Franklin Wilkins Building
5.9 Waterloo Bridge Wing
Waterloo Road
London SE1 9NH
Telephone 020 7848 4020/4070/4077
rec@kcl.ac.uk

09/07/2019

Alfonso Carlos Tamargo Robles

Dear Alfonso Carlos,

Internationalization of Andalusian companies during the last decade: reasons and perspectives

Thank you for submitting your Research Ethics Minimal Risk Registration Form. This letter acknowledges confirmation of your registration; your registration confirmation reference number is MRS-18/19-13972

Ethical clearance is granted and you may now commence data collection for this project.

Please note: For projects involving the use of an Information Sheet and Consent Form for recruitment purposes, please ensure that you use the KCL GDPR compliant [Information Sheet & Consent Form Templates](#)

Be sure to keep a record your registration number and include it in any materials associated with this research. Registration is valid for **one year** from today's date. Please note it is the responsibility of the researcher to ensure that any other permissions or approvals (i.e. R&D, gatekeepers, etc.) relevant to their research are in place, prior to conducting the research.

Record Keeping:

In addition, you are expected to keep records of your process of informed consent and the dates and relevant details of research covered by this application. For example, depending on the type of research that you are doing, you might keep:

- A record of the relevant details for public talks that you attend, the websites that visit, the interviews that you conduct
- The 'script' that you use to inform possible participants about what your research involves. This may include written information sheets, or the generic information you include in the emails you write to possible participants, or what you say to people when you approach them on the street for a survey, or the introductory material stated at the top of your on-line survey.
- Where appropriate, records of consent, e.g. copies of signed consent forms or emails where participants agree to be interviewed.

Audit:

You may be selected for an audit, to see how researchers are implementing this process. If audited, you will be expected to explain how your research abides by the general principles of ethical research. In particular, you will be expected to provide a general summary of your review of the possible risks involved in your research, as well as to provide basic research records (as above in Record Keeping) and to describe the process by which participants agreed to participate in your research.

Remember that if you have any questions about the ethical conduct of your research at any point, you should contact your supervisor (where applicable) or the Research Ethics office.

Feedback:

If you wish to provide any feedback on the process you may do so by emailing rec@kcl.ac.uk.

We wish you every success with this work.

With best wishes

Mr James Patterson

Research Ethics Office

Appendix 2. Information sheet for participants in the questionnaire

INFORMATION SHEET FOR PARTICIPANTS

Ethical Clearance Reference Number: *MRS-18/19-13972*

Internationalization of Andalusian companies during the last decade: reasons and perspectives

I would like to invite you to participate in this research project which forms part of my MSc International Marketing studies research. Before you decide whether you want to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what your participation will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information.

The purpose of the study is to research about the reasons that lead companies to carry out internationalization activities.

You are being invited to participate in this study because you have useful experience in international business development and management.

If you agree to take part you will complete a survey anonymously. The survey will ask you questions about why companies decide to internationalized. The survey will take you approximately 6-8 minutes and you will have to complete it only once.

Participation is completely voluntary. You should only take part if you want to and choosing not to take part will not disadvantage you in anyway. If you choose to take part you will be provide your consent by completing the survey. To do this you will be asked to indicate that you have read and understand the information provided and that you consent to your anonymous data being used for the purposes explained.

You are free to withdraw at any point during completion of the survey, without having to give a reason just closing your internet browser. Withdrawing from the study will not affect you in any way. Once you submit the survey, it will no longer be possible to withdraw from the study because the data will be fully anonymous. Please do not include any personal identifiable information in your responses.

This research is anonymous. This means that nobody, including the researchers, will be aware of your identity, and that nobody will be able to connect you to the answers you provide. Your answers will nevertheless be treated confidentially and the information you provide will not allow you to be identified in any research outputs/publications. Your data will be held securely using private electronic means during 1 year by King's Business School according to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The data controller for this project will be King's College London (KCL). Research is a task that the University carries out in the public interest. Your data will be processed in accordance with the standards set by the GDPR 2016.

The results of the study will be summarised in a dissertation project. The data will not be shared with any third party.

If you have any questions or require more information about this study, please contact me using the following contact details:

alfonso.tamargo_robles@kcl.ac.uk
(+34) 696 85 01 84

If this study has harmed you in any way or if you wish to make a complaint about the conduct of the study you can contact King's College London using the details below for further advice and information:

Professor Shintaro Okazaki
shintaro.okazaki@kcl.ac.uk
+44 (0)20 7836 5454 - Ext. 4122

Thank you for reading this information sheet and for considering taking part in this research.

Appendix 3. Examples of export ranking directory pages

Nº	EMPRESA	Productos exportados	CIFRA DE EXPORTACIÓN Miles de €	Dirección www	C.P. e-mail	Localidad teléfono	Principales países destino	Responsable Exportación
33	Fujitsu Ten España, S.A.	Equipos electrónicos para automoción	129.070	César Vallejo, 16 - Pol. Ind. Guadalhorce	29004 Málaga www.ftesa.es alcervantes@ftesa.es	952 13 30 00	Francia, Inglaterra, Turquía, R. Checa, Alemania, Polonia, EE.UU., Israel	Antonio Fdez. Cervantes
34	F.J. Sánchez Sucesores, S.A.U. La Pedriza	Aceite oliva, de pepita de uva, de girasol, aceitunas, alcaparras, encurtidos	122.236	Campañario, s/n 04270 Sorbas (Almería)	www.fjsanchez.com gabrielsanchez@fjsanchez.com	950 36 40 38	Europa, Asia, América	Gabriel Sánchez
35	Granada La Palma, S.C.A.	Hortofrutícola	121.602	N-340, Km. 342 18730 Carchuna (Granada)	www.granadalapalma.com carmelo@granadalapalma.com	958 62 39 03	Alemania, Reino Unido, Países Nórdicos, Holanda	Carmelo Salguero
36	Grupo Iturri	Vestuario y catzado laboral y de uniformidad, vehículos contra incendios	118.476	Avenida Roberto Osborne, 5 (PICA) 41007 Sevilla	www.iturri.com iturri@iturri.com	954 47 91 11	Portugal, Francia, Alemania, Chile, Inglaterra, Polonia, Argentina...	Francisco Javier Iturri Franco
37	Aceites Maeva, S.L.U.	Aceite de oliva	114.988	Avda. Incar, 8 - Parque Metropolitano 18130 Escúzar (Granada)	www.aceitesmaeva.com sales@aceitesmaeva.com	958 99 10 33	Europa, México, EE.UU., China y Japón	Mercedes Contreras Pulido
38	Evooil7, S.L.	AOVE, AOVE ecológico	112.000	Diego León, 4 - 4C 14002 Córdoba	www.esenciadecordoba.com antoniomoyano@esenciadecordoba.com	957 49 24 70	EE.UU. y Asia	Antonio Jesús Moyano
39	MP Ascensores	Sistemas de elevación	109.493	Leonardo Da Vinci, 15 - PCT Cartuja 41092 Sevilla	www.mpascensores.com hsj@mplifts.com	954 63 05 62	Francia, Austria, Holanda, Chequia, Rumania, Polonia, Rusia, México...	Hani Saliba Josam
40	Agro Sevilla Aceitunas, S.C.A.	Aceitunas de mesa y aceites de oliva	106.000	Paseo de Castel Madama, s/n 41590 La Roda de Andalucía (Sevilla)	www.agrosevilla.com grupo@agrosevilla.com	954 25 14 00	Arabia Saudita, Italia, EE.UU., R. Unido, Francia, Corea, India	Alfredo Martín Soldevilla
41	De Prado Quality Foods, S.L.	Aceite de oliva virgen extra, aceitunas y encurtidos	97.405	Alhaken II, Nº 8 14008 Córdoba	www.deprado.eu carmendeprado@deprado.eu	957 48 81 66	Portugal, Chile, EE.UU.	Carmen de Prado
42	S.C.A. Sta. Mª de la Rábida (Fresón de Palos)	Berries	96.000	Pol. Ind. San Jorge, calle B 21810 Palos Frontera (Huelva)	www.fresondepalos.es info@fresondepalos.es	959 65 60 20	Unión Europea principalmente	Antonio Oliveira
43	Surexport Compañía Agraria, S.L.	Fresa, frambuesa, mora y arándanos	92.950	Pol. Matalagrana, s/n - Apt. Correos 116 21730 Almonte (Huelva)	www.surexport.es carmen@surexport.es	959 45 15 50	Reino Unido, Austria, Países Bajos, Alemania, Suiza	Carmen Pérez Andrade
44	Grupo Alvic FR Mobiliario, S.L.*	Paneles, puertas para muebles	92.836	Carretera Alcalá La Real, s/n 23660 Alcaudete (Jaén)	www.grupoalvic.com jramirez@grupoalvic.com	953 56 20 02	Francia, USA, China, Alemania, Turquía, Rusia, México...	Julían Ramírez
45	Freshroyal, S.L.	Frutas de hueso y berries	92.500	Finca la Jarilla. Apartado 47 41300 San José de la Rinconada (Sevilla)	www.royal.es macgor@royal.es	955 79 06 00	Holanda, Francia, Alemania, Bélgica, Reino Unido	Macarena García-Otero
46	Fábrica, Madero y Despiece, SA FAMADESA	Carne de cerdo	89.422	Camino de Santa Inés, 71 29590 Campanillas (Málaga)	www.famadesa.es export@famadesa.es	952 43 30 50	Portugal y China	Juan Alberto Segura Escaño
47	Persán, S.A.	Jabones, detergentes y otros artículos de limpieza y abrillantamiento	87.600	Pino Albar, 2 41016 Sevilla	www.persan.es jmarribas@persan.es	954 99 83 50	Reino Unido, Portugal, Francia	Francisco Javier Fonseca
48	Frigoríficos Andaluces de Conservas de Carne, S.A. FACCSA	Carne y despojos de porcino, frescos y congelados	86.000	Plaza de Prolongo, 2 29580 Cartama Estación (Málaga)	www.faccsa.es export@faccsa.es	952 42 00 50	China, Francia, Portugal, Japón	Ramón Soler Ciurana
49	Derehil, S.A.	Industria química. Danoxi, Danfenil	83.970	Bda. Villaricos 04616 Cuevas Almanzora (Almería)	www.derehil.com antonio.arroyo@derehil.com	950 61 80 00	Singapur	Antonio Arroyo
50	Torraspapel, S.A.*	Papeles estucados 2C y papel para etiquetas	82.000	Camino de la Vía, s/n 18600 Motril (Granada)	www.lecta.com info@lecta.com	958 83 20 00	EE.UU., Canadá, Francia, México, Portugal, Chile, Turquía, Colombia...	Conrado Lignana Xavier Biosca
51	Aceites Abasa, S.A.	Aceite de oliva	81.000	Avda. Alemania, s/n 14850 Baena (Córdoba)	www.aceitesabasa.com daniel.perez@aceitesabasa.com	957 67 04 00	EE.UU., Canadá, China, Japón, Australia, Corea del Sur, Vietnam...	Daniel Perez
52	Hortofrutícola Mabe S.A.T.	Pimiento, pepino, calabacín, berenjena, melón y sandía	80.000	Polígono La Redonda C/ VII - Nº 35 04710 El Ejido (Almería)	www.mabesat.com aruz@mabesat.com	950 58 33 00	Toda Europa	Antonio Ruiz Torres
53	Cooperativa Agrícola San Isidro CASI	Tomates	78.867	Ctra. Nijar, s/n - Los Partidores 04120 La Cañada (Almería)	www.casi.es msegura@casi.es	950 62 60 07	Toda la Unión Europea	Manuel Segura Sánchez
54	Berrynest SAT H-0023	Fresón, frambuesa, arándano, mora, cítricos, boniato	78.400	Ctra. Almonte - El Rocío, Km. 9.5 21730 Almonte (Huelva)	www.bionest.es thomas@bionest.es	959 45 06 56	UK, Alemania, Suiza, Francia	Thomas Cera
55	Grupo Transonuba	Transporte: productos en seco, refrigerados y congelados	77.466	Polígono Los Bermejales, Parcela 8 21840 Niebla (Huelva)	www.transonuba.es jrsanchez@transonuba.es	959 36 38 50	Alemania, Francia, UK, Países Bajos	José R. Sánchez Márquez
56	Calconut, S.L.	Frutos secos, fruta desecada y especias	76.000	Avda. Europa, 5. Pta. Alta 04648 San Juan de los Terreros (Almería)	www.calconut.com logistics@calconut.es	950 61 93 77	Francia, Argelia, Italia, Brasil, Latinoamérica	Julia Borí
57	Bodegas Williams & Humbert, S.A.	Sherry, brandy de Jerez, destilados...	75.895	N-IV, Km. 641,75 11408 Jerez Frontera (Cádiz)	www.williams-humbert.com alfonso.roidan@williams-humbert.com	956 35 34 01	Filipinas, USA, Alemania, Francia, Reino Unido, República Checa	Alfonso Roldán Piñero
58	Eurocastell Caña, S.L.	Tomate cherry, pepino holandés, calabacín	75.358	Pago del Rancho, s/n 18740 Castell de Ferro (Granada)	www.eurocastell.com antonio_garcia@mgsehijos.es	958 83 04 06	Alemania, Reino Unido, Francia, Holanda,	Antonio García Puerta
59	Asean Brown Boveri, S.A. * ABB	Transformadores de potencia (tecnologías columnas y acorazados)	75.000	Escritor Conde Zamora, s/n 14004 Córdoba	www.new.abb.com/es miguel.oliva@es.abb.com	91 581 93 93	África, Europa, Asia, Sudamérica	Miguel Oliva
60	Sensient Fragrances, S.A.	Aceites esenciales, productos químicos aromáticos y fragancias	74.868	Carretera Armilla, Km. 2,5 18100 Armilla (Granada)	www.sensientflavorsandfragrances.com	958 18 30 03	A nivel mundial	Pedro García Navarro
61	Aceitunas Guadalquivir, S.L.	Aceitunas de mesa en todos sus formatos	74.000	Vereda La Alcobá, 2 A 41530 Morón Frontera (Sevilla)	www.agolives.com fjescalante@agolives.com	955 85 47 10	EE.UU., Europa	Francisco Javier Escalante Terrón
62	S.A.T. 9855 Primaflor	Lechugas en todas sus variedades, ajos, cebollas	73.315	La Estación, 2 04640 Pulpi (Almería)	www.primaflor.com ecorroba@primaflor.com	950 46 40 11	Europa, Oriente Próximo, Canadá	Eduardo Córdoba
63	Thielmann Portinnox Spain, S.A.	Contenedores de acero inoxidable para bebidas	70.000	Ctra. Puliñanas, km. 6 18197 Puliñanas (Granada)	www.thielmann.com rafael.garcés@thielmann.com	958 40 60 00	EE.UU., México	Rafael Garcés
64	Biosabor S.A.T.	Hortalizas ecológicas, gazpacho, salmorejo, salsas	65.000	Ctra. San José, Km. 2 04117 San Isidro de Nijar (Almería)	www.biosabor.com jcastillo@biosabor.com	950 70 01 00	Toda Europa	Juan Francisco Castillo García

Ranking por volumen de EXPORTACIÓN

Nº	EMPRESA	Productos exportados	CIFRA DE EXPORTACIÓN Miles de €	Dirección C.P. Localidad www e-mail teléfono	Principales países destino	Responsable Exportación
65	Trops S.A.T. 2803	Agua y mango	63.450	Apartado Correos 84 - Pol. El Trapiche 29700 Vélez Málaga (Málaga) www.trops.es martina@trops.es 952 50 07 00	Europa, Europa del Este, Sudáfrica	Martina Otten
66	Grupo AM Tiresur, S.L.	Neumáticos	62.626	Orson Wells, 2 18197 Pularanas (Granada) www.grupoam.es eluque@tiresur.com 958 16 19 13	Portugal, Brasil, Colombia, Bolivia, El Salvador, Argentina, Chile, Perú...	Emilio Luque
67	Moguer Cuna de Platero, S.C.A.	Fresas, frambuesas, arándanos, moras	59.000	Camino Montemayor, s/n 21800 Moguer (Huelva) www.cunadeplatero.com sergiosainz@cunadeplatero.com 959 37 21 25	Alemania, Francia, Italia, Suiza, Austria, P. Bajos, Portugal, Suecia	Sergio Sáinz Seguí
68	José Luis Montosa, S.L. Frutas Montosa	Agua y mango, guacamole y mango procesado	56.500	Finca El Molino, s/n - Valle Niza 29792 Vélez Málaga (Málaga) www.frutasmontosa.com comercial@frutasmontosa.com 952 51 35 33	Francia, Italia, Dinamarca, Bélgica, Holanda, Alemania...	Carlos Ojeda
69	Siderúrgica Sevillana, S.A. SISE	Barra de acero de distintas secciones y diámetros	55.000	A-92, Km. 6 - Pol. Hacienda Dolores 41500 Alcalá Guadaíra (Sevilla) marco.samoré@rivagroup.com 954 97 93 00	Europa y otros países de la cuenca mediterránea	Marco Samoré Martín
70	IBP Atcosa, S.L.	Accesorios de tubería de cobre	54.568	Polligono Industrial Quintos Aeropuerto, s/n 14005 Córdoba www.ibpatcosa.com josemiguel.rueda@ibpgroup.com 957 46 96 00	UK, Polonia, Portugal, Francia, Argelia	José Miguel Rueda Arroyo
71	Grupo Osborne	Bebidas espirituosas, vinos, jamones y paletas ibéricas	54.000	Fernán Caballero, 7 11500 El Puerto de Santa María (Cádiz) www.osborne.es amelia.rodriguez@osborne.es 956 86 90 00	Alemania, Holanda, México, Canadá, EE.UU., China	Jaime Fdez. / Rene Lemee
72	Plastienvase, S.L. SP Group	Láminas flexibles, rígidas, semi-rígidas para envasado alimentación	51.000	Carretera Palma del Río, Km. 10 14710 Villarrubia (Córdoba) www.spg-pack.com agutierrez@spg-pack.com 957 76 76 12	Polonia, Alemania, Francia, Portugal, Benelux, G. Bretaña, Irlanda, Rusia...	Andrés Gutiérrez de Ravé
73	Coprohijar, S.C.A.	Tomate (cherry, baby pera, rama, pera, cocktail...), calabacín y sandía	50.000	Antonio Castillo, 1 04117 San Isidro Nijar (Almería) www.coprohijar.com comerciales@coprohijar.net 950 36 60 15	Unión Europea	Miguel Pérez López
74	Grupo Ybarra Alimentación, S.L.	Aceites, vinagres, mayonesas, salsas y aceitunas	48.750	Carretera Isla Menor, Km. 1.8 41703 Dos Hermanas (Sevilla) www.ybarragroup.com exportacion@grupoybarra.es 955 67 50 60	China, Noruega, Brasil, India, Japón, Polonia, México...	Tristán Ybarra Sáinz de la Maza
75	Sotrafa, S.A.	Cubiertas invernadero, acolchados, films y bolsas ensilaje, geosintéticos...	47.580	Paraje Cartabona, 12 - Sta. Mª del Águila 04710 El Ejido (Almería) www.sotrafa.com export2@sotrafa.com 950 40 56 00	Francia R. Unido, Italia, Marruecos, Chile, Argentina, EEUU, Turquía...	Vicente Cejas Medina
76	Agrupapulpí, S.A.	Lechuga, sandía, melón, brócoli, apio	46.473	Carretera Pulpi-Terreros, Km. 0.7 04640 Pulpi (Almería) www.agrupapulpí.es pedidos@agrupapulpí.com 950 46 41 54	Alemania, Italia, Reino Unido, Noruega y otros	Rodrigo Soler Sánchez
77	Sociedad Financiera y Minera, S.A. FYM *	Cemento y clínker	45.000	Carretera Almería, Km. 8 29720 Málaga www.heidelbergcement.es info@heidelbergcement.es 952 20 91 00	Gambia, Argelia, Ghana, Argentina, Francia, Irlanda	Jesús Ortiz Used
78	Procavi, S.L.	Pechuga, contramuslo, picada de jamón, alón, etc.	44.700	Carretera Comarcal 339, Km. 23.6 41620 Marchena (Sevilla) www.procavi.es franciscojose.aguera@turkeylovers.es 955 84 78 79	Francia, Portugal, Alemania, Benin	Ángel de la Torre Blandon
79	Hortofrutícola Costa de Almería, S.L.	Pepino, pimiento, tomate, calabacín, berenjena, judía verde	44.260	Plaza Huerta de Europa, 1 04740 Roquetas Mar (Almería) www.hcostadéalmeria.es e.vargas@hcostadéalmeria.es 950 32 62 32	Alemania, Francia, Holanda, Italia, Gran Bretaña	Enrique Vargas Garbín
80	Oni Foods Ovearseas, S.L.	Carne y pescado congelados	44.018	Alameda Principal, 2 - 1ª Planta 29005 Málaga 952 60 80 00 www.onifoods.com flamed@onifoods.com	Egipto, Nigeria, Ghana, Costa Marfil, Togo, Benin, Gabón, Hong Kong...	Farouk Hamed
81	Tighleef Industries, S.L.U. Derprosa	Artes gráficas, food packaging y etiquetas	42.600	Avenida Iberoamérica, 56 23680 Alcalá la Real (Jaén) www.derprosa.com staff.es@ti-films.com 953 59 81 00	Europa central, EEUU y China	Ignacio López-Baillo
82	Elmya, S.A.	Energía renovable	41.144	Alonso Carrillo, 16 41007 Sevilla www.elmya.com cpinar@elmya.com 954 57 94 90	Reino Unido, Perú, Emiratos Árabes Unidos, México, Argentina, Chile	Carlos Piñar
83	Clarton Horn, S.A.	Fabricación de equipos eléctricos del automóvil (cláxones)	39.200	Avenida Juan Carlos I, s/n 23200 La Carolina (Jaén) www.clartonhorn.com info@clartonhorn.com 953 01 13 00	Europa, Asia y América	Guillermo Vaca
84	Almendras Utrera, S.L.	Almendras	39.100	Almería, s/n 04957 Albánchez (Almería) miguel@almaztrasutreracom 950 44 92 11	Alemania, Italia, EE.UU., Francia, India, Grecia	Miguel Utrera
85	TDK Electronics Components, SAU	Condensadores	39.029	Severo Ochoa, 66-68 (PTA) 29590 Campanillas (Málaga) 952 64 83 24 www.tdk-electronics.tdk.com karen.schoenrogge@tdk-electronics.tdk.com	Alemania, China, Rusia	Karen Schoenrogge
86	Grupo Almendras Francisco Morales	Almendras, Industrializado, pralinés, nuez, pistachos, anacardos...	36.137	Carretera Camponubes, s/n 14814 Zamoranos (Córdoba) contable@almaztrasutreracom 957 55 60 06	Portugal, Este Europa, Francia, Marruecos, A. Saudí, E. Árabes...	Francisco Morales Jiménez
87	Nature Choice S.A.T.	Pepino, pimiento, tomate, berenjena, calabacín, sandía, melón	36.016	Ctra. Almerimar, nº 24 04700 El Ejido (Almería) 950 60 77 77 www.naturechoice-sat.com dircomercial@naturechoice-sat.com	Alemania, Suecia, Dinamarca, Francia, Noruega, R. Checa, Holanda	Manuel Arévalo Barazas
88	Destilaciones Bordas Chinchurreta, S.A.	Industria química: perfumería	36.000	Acueducto, 4 - Pol. Ctra. La Isla 41703 Dos Hermanas (Sevilla) www.bordas-sa.com bordas@bordas-sa.com 954 41 90 00	Los 5 continentes	Ramón Bordas Cuéllar
89	Indasol S.A.T. 9404	Pepino, pimiento, berenjena, calabacín, melón, sandía	35.969	Apartado Correos 56 - Paraje los Aljibillos 04700 El Ejido (Almería) www.indasol.es ramon@indasol.es 950 48 82 50	Francia, Alemania, Inglaterra, Países del Este	Ramón Barbero Fernández
90	Oleoestepa, S.C.A. 2º Grado	Aceite de oliva virgen extra granel y envasado	34.196	El Olivo, s/n - Pol. Ind. Sierra Sur 41560 Estepa (Sevilla) www.oleoestepa.com export@oleoestepa.com 955 91 31 54	Francia, Italia, EE.UU., China y Japón	Luis Felipe Montero
91	Grupo Forma 5, S.L.U.	Mobiliario para oficinas	34.000	Acueducto, 12 / 14 - Pol. Ctra. La Isla 41700 Dos Hermanas (Sevilla) www.forma5.com rfernandez@forma5.com 954 93 19 80	Francia, EAU, UK, Arabia Saudí	Rubén Fernández Parrado
92	Bio-Oils Hueva, S.L.	Biodiesel, glicerina	33.705	Gobernador A. Horcujadas - P. Nuevo Puerto 21810 Palos Frontera (Huelva) www.bio-oils.com alejandro.mora@bio-oils.com 959 36 98 96	China, India, Malasia, Ucrania, Turquía, Portugal, Italia, Francia	Alejandro Mora
93	Alter Technology TÜV NORD	Espacio. Componentes electrónicos de alta fiabilidad	33.106	Tomás Alba Edison, 4 - PCT Cartuja 41092 Sevilla 954 46 70 50 www.altertechnology.com german.cuello@altertechnology.com	Europa, Argentina, Brasil, Rusia y China	Germán Cuello
94	Peninsular del Latón, S.A.	Barra de latón	32.240	Avenida de la Fábrica, s/n 14005 Córdoba www.pdlaton.es jglesias@pdlaton.es 957 46 35 85	Italia, Marruecos, Portugal, Túnez, Alemania	José Mª Iglesias de Blas
95	Miguel García Sánchez e Hijos, S.A.	Tomate cherry, aguacate, mango	32.216	Carretera Vieja de Carchuna, s/n 18600 Motril (Granada) 958 82 51 82 www.miguelgarciasanchezhijos.com antonio_garcia@mgsehijos.es	Alemania, Reino Unido, Francia, Holanda	Antonio García Puerta
96	AGO Labs	Servicios tecnológicos. Asesoría y ensayos analíticos	31.771	Avenida de la Palmera, 27 41013 Sevilla www.agqlabs.com ptorres@agqlabs.com 955 73 89 08	Chile, Perú, USA, Colombia, México, Marruecos, Argentina, Costa Rica...	Pedro Torres Rey

Appendix 4. Additional tables

Table 4: Frequency distribution of reasons for internationalization

TABLE 4
Frequency distribution of reasons for internationalization (nominal scale)

	Internal		External			Mixed		Others	Total	
	Internal Strategic Decisions	Entrepreneurial character of the Management	National market didn't allow growth	International markets offered opportunities	2008 economic crisis	Public programs	Competitors movements			Clients movements
<i>As first option</i>	22.6	18	19.1	30.3	4.5	1.1	1.1	2.2	1.1	100
<i>As second option</i>	33.7	10.1	10.1	28.1	7.9	3.4	1.1	3.4	2.2	100

Table 5: Frequency distribution for 2008 crisis

TABLE 5
Frequency distribution for 2008 crisis (Likert scale)

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Total
<i>2008 crisis has influenced the internationalization of Andalusian companies</i>	2.2	5.6	10.1	52.8	29.3	100
<i>2008 crisis has boosted the internationalization of Andalusian companies</i>	2.2	4.5	11.2	52.8	29.3	100

Table 6: Frequency distribution for public programs to promote internationalization

TABLE 6
Frequency distribution for public programs to promote internationalization (Likert scale)

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Total
<i>Programs that promote and support internationalization developed by public institutions are useful</i>	0	5.6	10.1	56.2	28.1	100
<i>Government programs that promote and support internationalization have influenced the internationalization of Andalusian companies</i>	1.1	4.5	20.2	51.7	22.5	100

Table 7: Classification of participating companies

TABLE 7
Classification of participating companies

	< 10	10 - 20	20 - 30	30 - 40	> 40	Total	
<i>Number of countries with commercial or productive activity</i>	17.9	16.9	29.2	13.5	22.5	100	
	< 10%	10 - 25%	25 - 50%	50 - 75%	> 75%	n/a	Total
<i>% of employees work in foreign markets</i>	30.3	14.6	18	22.5	10.1	4.5	100
<i>% of total sales in international markets</i>	5.6	15.7	18	32.6	23.6	4.5	100
	< 2	2 - 10	10 - 50	50 - 10	> 100	n/a	Total
<i>Total sales (million euros)</i>	10.1	9	42.7	14.6	18	5.6	100

Appendix 5: Questionnaire

1. *How would you describe your company's internationalization activities in the last 10 years?*

- *Very low intensity or importance*
- *Low intensity or importance*
- *Moderate intensity or importance*
- *High intensity or importance*
- *Very high intensity or importance*

2. *What is the main reason why your company has developed internationalization activities in the last 10 years?*

- *Internal strategic decisions*
- *Entrepreneurial character of the Management*
- *Competitors' movements*
- *Customers' movements*
- *Domestic market did not allow significant growth*
- *International markets offered good opportunities*
- *Economic crisis that began in 2008*
- *Public programs to promote internationalization*
- *Other reasons*

3. *What is the second main reason why your company has developed internationalization activities in the last 10 years?*

- *Internal strategic decisions*
- *Entrepreneurial character of the Management*
- *Competitors' movements*
- *Customers' movements*
- *Domestic market did not allow significant growth*
- *International markets offered good opportunities*
- *Economic crisis that began in 2008*
- *Public programs to promote internationalization*
- *Other reasons*

4. *When it comes to making internationalization decisions, how do internal factors (strategic or company-specific factors) and external factors (company environment and market factors) influence?*

- *Internal factors are the most important*
- *Internal factors are the most important, although external factors are also considered*
- *Internal and external factors are equally considered*
- *External factors are the most important, although internal factors are also considered*
- *External factors are the most important*

5. *When it comes to making internationalization decisions, how do strategic vision of the company's Management and the competitive environment of the company influence?*

- *Strategic vision of the Management is the most important*
- *Strategic vision of the Management is the most important, although the competitive environment is also considered*
- *Strategic vision of the Management and competitive environment have the same influence*
- *Competitive environment is the most important, although the strategic vision of the Management is also considered*
- *Competitive environment is the most important*

6. *The strategic vision of the Management and the internal specific factors of your company have influenced the internationalization process*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*

- *Agree*
 - *Strongly agree*
7. *Your company always seeks to be leader in the international markets in which it is present*
- *Strongly disagree*
 - *Disagree*
 - *Neither agree nor disagree*
 - *Agree*
 - *Strongly agree*
8. *Of the following, what is the main reason why your company has internationalized?*
- *Search for new strategic resources*
 - *Search for new markets and new customers*
 - *Search for commercial and/or productive efficiencies*
 - *Search for new strategic assets*
 - *Other motives*
9. *Your company has internationalized in response to competitors' movements*
- *Strongly disagree*
 - *Disagree*
 - *Neither agree nor disagree*
 - *Agree*
 - *Strongly agree*
10. *Your company has internationalized following competitors' example or steps*
- *Strongly disagree*
 - *Disagree*
 - *Neither agree nor disagree*
 - *Agree*
 - *Strongly agree*
11. *Your company has internationalized in response to clients' movements*
- *Strongly disagree*
 - *Disagree*
 - *Neither agree nor disagree*
 - *Agree*
 - *Strongly agree*

12. *Your company has internationalized following the steps or needs of its clients*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

13. *Your company has internationalized due to the local or national market situation*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

14. *Your company has internationalized because the local or national market did not offer real growth opportunities*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

15. *Your company has internationalized due to existing opportunities in international markets*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

16. *Your company has internationalized because international markets offered opportunities to grow*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

17. *The economic-financial crisis that began in 2008 and its consequences have influenced the internationalization of your company*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

18. *The economic-financial crisis of 2008 contributed or boosted the internationalization of your company*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

19. *In general, the economic-financial crisis that began in 2008 has influenced the internationalization of Andalusian companies*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

20. *In general, the economic-financial crisis of 2008 has boosted the internationalization of Andalusian companies*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

21. *Has your company participated in activities or programs that promote the internationalization of companies developed by institutions such as ICEX (Government of Spain), EXTENDA (Government of Andalusia), Chambers of Commerce, etc.?*

- *No, we have never participated*
- *We have participated sporadically*
- *We have participated in some activities*

- *Yes, we have participated in many activities*
- *Yes, we have participated regularly and actively*

22. *The programs that promote and support internationalization developed by public institutions are useful*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

23. *Government programs that support internationalization have influenced the internationalization of your company*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

24. *In general, government programs that promote and support internationalization have influenced the internationalization of Andalusian companies*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

25. *The internationalization activities developed by your company have contributed to achieving the strategic objectives*

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

26. *The internationalization activities developed by your company have contributed to the growth of the company*

- *Strongly disagree*

- *Disagree*
- *Neither agree nor disagree*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

27. *Approximately, how many countries does your company have commercial or productive activity?*

- *Less than 10*
- *Between 10 and 20*
- *Between 20 and 30*
- *Between 30 and 40*
- *More than 40*

28. *Approximately, what percentage of your company's employees work in foreign markets? (countries other than the country of origin of the company) (Optional)*

- *Less than 10%*
- *Between 10% and 25%*
- *Between 25% and 50%*
- *Between 50% and 75%*
- *More than 75%*

29. *Approximately, what percentage of your company's total sales corresponds to international markets? (Optional)*

- *Less than 10%*
- *Between 10% and 25%*
- *Between 25% and 50%*
- *Between 50% and 75%*
- *More than 75%*

30. *Approximately, what are the total sales of your company? (national and international) (Optional)*

- *Less than 2 million euros*
- *Between 2 and 10 million euros*
- *Between 10 and 50 million euros*
- *Between 50 and 100 million euros*
- *More than 100 million euros*

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